

Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews

Subekti, A., Supriyadi, & Indrayanti, K. W. (2023). Legal Strategies to Enforce Military Discipline for Personnel of Indonesian Armed Forces at the Army Aviation Center. *Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews*, 2(2), 42-53.

ISSN 2827-9735

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1996.02.02.58

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews is a peer-reviewed International Journal of the Asian Institute of Research. The journal covers scholarly articles in the interdisciplinary fields of law and humanities, including constitutional and administrative law, criminal law, civil law, international law, linguistics, history, literature, performing art, philosophy, religion, visual arts, anthropology, culture, and ethics studies. The Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews is an Open Access Journal that can be accessed and downloaded online for free. Thus, ensuring high visibility and increase of citations for all research articles published. The journal aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of law.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Legal Strategies to Enforce Military Discipline for Personnel of Indonesian Armed Forces at the Army Aviation Center

Arie Subekti¹, Supriyadi¹, Kadek Wiwik Indrayanti¹

¹ Faculty of Law, University of Merdeka, Malang, Indonesia

Correspondence: Kadek Wiwik Indrayanti, University of Merdeka, Malang, Indonesia,
E-mail: kadek.wiwik@unmer.ac.id

Abstract

It is compulsory for Indonesian Armed Forces at Army Aviation Center (AAC) to demonstrate military discipline and uphold military ethics pursuant to *Sapta Marga* and *Sumpah Prajurit* (Oath of Enlistment). The law of military discipline is governed by several laws in Indonesia to maintain and enforce the professionalism of privates. However, in the armed forces at AAC, there had been at least 28 violations of military disciplines from 2017-2022. This research aims to analyze the causes of these violations and formulate the proper strategies to help improve law enforcement in military discipline for the armed forces at AAC. The research results reveal that nine factors have triggered the violations of military discipline among privates in AAC, including poor understanding of the law, poor organizational culture, socio-cultural factors, personality, motivation, psychological conditions, a shortage of natural resources, inadequate sanction, leadership, family problems, and economic burdens. To tackle all those factors causing violations of military disciplines, this research formulates 7 strategies to enhance law enforcement in military discipline for armed forces, consisting of strict law enforcement, training and education, administrative sanctions, enforcement of rules and regulations, strong organizational cultures, reinforced focus on career building, openness, and transparency.

Keywords: Legal Policy, Enforcement of Military Discipline, Indonesian Armed Forces, Army Aviation Center

1. Introduction

Indonesian Armed Forces are a military organization established to protect and maintain the security and the sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia (Yogo, 2016). To execute related tasks, the armed forces, especially those based at the Army Aviation Center (henceforth referred to as AAC, are required to strongly adhere to and uphold military discipline and ethics according to *Sapta Marga* and *Sumpah Prajurit* (henceforth referred to as oath of enlistment) (Tentara Nasional Indonesia, 2023). The enforcement of military discipline is considered vital among the armed forces, considering that it ensures that privates comply with existing regulations and standards and that they professionally perform their tasks (Dewan Perwakilan Rakyat Republik Indonesia, 2009).

According to Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian Armed Forces (henceforth referred to as Law No 34/2004), professionalism serves as one of the primary criteria for the armed forces, involving: (Hadisancoko, 2019) 1. Expertise and competence: a. The privates in the armed forces must demonstrate expertise and competence relevant to the tasks and responsibility in training, skill development, and application of technology, 2. Integrity and responsibilities: the privates in the armed forces must fully demonstrate integrity and responsibilities and act according to appropriate norms and ethics and perform responsibilities in executing tasks and governmental tasks. 3. The ability to establish coordination and cooperation: the privates of the armed forces must demonstrate the ability to establish coordination and cooperation appropriately with several parties including governmental institutions, mass organizations, and society in general, 4. The ability to adapt and ride and drive: the privates of the armed forces must be able to adapt to environmental changes and changing situations, and they must demonstrate the ability to ride and drive and establish coordination appropriately to support their tasks and governmental tasks. 5. Openness and transparency: the privates of the armed forces must demonstrate openness and transparency in executing their tasks and governmental tasks and ensure that information and reports delivered to the public are accurate and accountable.

To meet those criteria, the legal policy and enforcement of military disciplines become vital instruments to ensure that the tasks and responsibilities are appropriately performed by the privates of the armed forces in the domain of AAC (Pusat Pendidikan Markas Besar Tentara Nasional Indonesia, 2006). The legal basis of the military discipline is set forth in Law Number 25 of 2014 concerning Military Discipline Law (henceforth referred to as Law No. 25/2014). Law No. 25/2014 governs disciplinary law among the members of the armed forces, highlighting the conduct that leads to the imposition of disciplinary sanctions and the procedures and mechanisms of the enforcement of disciplinary law in the Indonesian Armed Forces. Several main points were made in Law No. 25/2014, including 1) the legal standing and tasks in Indonesian Armed Forces, 2) the types of conduct that can be given sanctions among the members of the armed forces, including standing against disciplines, the conduct that harms the armed forces, conduct that harms public, and any conduct contravening the norms existing in society, 3) the procedures and mechanisms of the enforcement of disciplinary law involve investigation of the conduct, sanction imposition, and follow-up of judicial decisions, 4) the elections and the tasks of disciplinary judges, 5) the protection of the members of Indonesian Armed Forces and Indonesian National Police serving disciplinary sanctions; this protection should protect their rights during the investigation, sanction imposition, and follow-up.

Law No. 25/2014 is expected to enhance the disciplinary norms among the members of the armed forces and Indonesian National Police and to further reinforce the integrity and professionalism in executing the tasks and responsibilities as the protectors of the public (Upe, 2011). To some extent, the enforcement of military discipline also helps ensure that privates understand their responsibilities as members of the public and uphold the national value and ethics in society. This also maintains the reputation of the Armed Forces and ensures that the privates receive respect from the members of the public (Chandra, 2020).

In order to enforce military discipline, the Indonesian Armed Forces adhere to strict procedures and mechanisms, including the sanctions enforced for the privates who violate rules and norms. It ensures that privates understand the importance of discipline and cooperation and that the armed forces are a professional and respected military organization.

However, Law No. 34/2004 and Law No. 25/2014 cannot accommodate all the issues faced by the armed forces, especially at AAC. Thus, a more operational policy that fits the need and the current development is required. Moreover, more strategic changes in the environment relevant to the dynamic, complexity, and heavier challenges in the future highly require the privates or personnel Armed Forces at AAC to keep improving the credibility, professionalism, and productivity to build a more effective, efficient, and measurable work system.

Departing from the above introduction, this research aims to study the legal policy and the enforcement of military discipline among the members of the Armed Forces at AAC.

2. Military Disciplinary Law: An Introduction

Article 1 point 2 of Law Number 25/2014 defines the definition of military discipline as “awareness, compliance, and adherence to implementing statutory regulations, official regulations, and the life of military people”. Meanwhile, the law of military discipline can be understood as “regulations and norms governing, training, enforcing discipline and the life of of the military personnel”.

Furthermore, the law of military discipline is responsible to provide organizational and personnel training to help improve the military discipline and to enforce the law of military discipline by considering merit and justice according to *Pancasila* and the 1945 Constitution of Indonesia as governed in Article 4 and Article 5 of Law No. 25/2014 (Wulansari, n.d.). The law of military discipline also serves to a. assure legal certainty and legal protection for military personnel and to avert the likelihood of the abuse of power to punish (commonly referred to as *Ankum*); and b. enforce the community life of military personnel in performing their tasks and obligations. To implement the law of military discipline, several principles need to be taken into account: a. justice; b. training; c. equality before law; d. presumption of innocence; e. hierarchy; f. commander unity; f. military interest; g. obligations; h. effectiveness and efficiency; and i. merit.

Privates are subject to military disciplinary punishment if they violate laws and/or military disciplinary rules and/or take actions contravening military life regulated in *Sapta Marga* and Oath of Enlistment.

The severity levels of the violations of disciplinary rules among the privates of the Indonesian Armed Forces range from mild, medium, to serious. The first category refers to violations only affecting a small military unit, the second category refers to violations leaving negative impacts on the whole institution of the Armed Forces, while the serious violations refer to infringements causing serious impacts on the government and the state (Herawati et al., 2014).

Disciplinary military punishment is imposed by the top official on the subordinates under their command. The violations subject to military punishment involve: a. all conduct mentioned in related law with three-month imprisonment as the minimum punishment or six-month imprisonment as the maximum punishment; b. ordinary cases that do not require complex evidence; c. criminal offenses that do not hamper military interest and/or public interest; d. criminal offenses caused by the absence of a person without consent within a four-day resolution period.

Article 9 and Article 10 of Law No. 25/2014 elaborate on the types of punishment imposed on privates committing violations: 1. Warning; 2. Mild disciplinary restrictions for 14 days; or 3. Serious disciplinary restrictions for not more than 21 days; military disciplinary law imposition followed by administrative sanctions according to the provisions of rules and regulations.

However, the punishment as in Article 9 and Article 10 can be aggravated if the cases concerned fulfill certain conditions by adding 7 more days of restrictions. These certain conditions involve: 1) a state in an emergency as specified in legislation, 2) a military operation to support the execution of main tasks of the Indonesian Armed Forces, including military operation for battles or other matters other than battles according to the legislation, 3) the prepared unit to execute the military operation for battles and military operation for matters other than battles according to the legislation, 4) military matters involving repeated violations of military disciplines in six months after the imposition of military disciplinary law.

In terms of organizational scope, the top military officials (*Ankum*) are authorized to punish subordinates under their commands. In terms of the enforcement of disciplinary law among privates of the armed forces, *Ankum* hold three categories of authority: (a) *Ankum* are fully authorized to impose all kinds of punishment to subordinates under their commands, but not including serious disciplinary restrictions imposed on commissioned officers, and (c) *Ankum* have restricted authority to issue a warning for and impose mild restrictions on non-commissioned officers and enlisted personnel under their commands. Thus, military disciplinary punishment is principally related to restrictions and implementation of order within the internal scope of disciplinary violations committed by the privates of the Armed Forces, in addition to the violations settled at Court Martial and public courts.

3. Cases and Factors causing Disciplinary Violations in Indonesian Armed Forces at Army Aviation Center

Army Aviation Center (AAC) serving as an organ of the Indonesian Armed Forces is a central implementer in the aviation of the Indonesian Armed Forces positioned under the Chief of the Staff of Indonesian Armed Forces (commonly referred to as KSAD). The AAC is responsible to organize flight operations in the armed forces to back up the main tasks of the armed forces.

Article 7 of Law No. 25/2014 states that military personnel must comply with the law of military discipline. That is, the personnel of the armed forces are required to abide by their top officials and they must protect the reputation and avert any conduct that can defame the reputation of the army and its units. The military personnel violating rules are subject to punishment with no particular treatment involved, and judicial investigation is carried out according to the procedures of court martial as governed in Law Number 31 of 1997 concerning Court Martial.

A private or a member of the armed forces is required to follow stricter disciplinary rules compared to civilians, and this particular condition sets particular legal principle as relevant to the principle of *Lex Specialist Derogat Legi Generale*, meaning that certain rules (Military Penal Code) will rule out the laws that apply to civilians (the Penal Code) (Saputra, 2019).

There are several grounds leading to specific and stricter sanction imposition for privates or personnel of the armed forces following the violations committed (Haryo Sulistiryanto, 2011): a) Some conduct considered as violations committed by the personnel of armed forces but this specification does not apply to civilians such as desertion, refusing to perform official tasks, insubordination, and others, b) conduct that is considered severe but when the criminal sanctions are imposed, this is deemed too lenient.

If all those matters were to be set forth in the Penal Code, it would be hard to implement since these matters only apply to certain members of the community, and the violations are only settled at court-martial.

The Regulation of the Commander of Indonesian Armed Forces Number Perpang/45/VII/2008 concerning Master Guidelines of Training of Personnel and Military Manpower of Indonesian Armed Forces in Annex Chapter III regarding Privates Training in Indonesian Armed Forces, especially regarding disciplinary training, social order, and law state that the discipline and order are the main pillars in the enforcement of army life reflected in the mentality and attitude in the conduct and services. The objectives of disciplinary training, order, and law are to 1) produce responsible privates complying with the current legislation, provisions, and rules and with the command given by commanders, 2) to shape privates and their families as examples of the society, which is intended to foster harmonious conditions of the community, 3) to assure good order/peace stemming from the legal awareness of privates and their families and to ensure that tasks are fully addressed to the interest of the Armed Forces.

Indonesian Armed Forces are required to have their role in the training for the subordinates according to the authority set forth in Article 69 of Law Number 31 of 1997, implying that high military officials as enquirers authorized to impose sanctions are assisted by Military Police as enquirers in the scope of Indonesian Armed Force. This stage is given a follow-up by Military Prosecutors and a commander of the unit with double main functions: (a) Ankum and (b) case officers (commonly referred to as Papera). Therefore, a unit military commander can hand in the criminal cases of the military members concerned to court-martial, while military police serve as enquirers. As Ankum, a unit commander is only responsible for the tasks given in the unit, and security is handled by the military police department. (Pusat Penerangan Tentara Nasional Indonesia, 2014). therefore, military discipline represents military vigor to protect and support military discipline in a wider definition, enabling the Indonesian Armed Forces to execute tasks and obligations appropriately. It also means that both military members and civilians intending to spoil military discipline are subject to military law and both are judged under military judicial systems (Tambunan, 2005).

In the last five years (2017-2022), there had been several violations of military disciplinary law at AAC, ranging from personal-related cases such as domestic violence or other matters related to official affairs such as desertion. The following Table shows violations of disciplinary law among privates and enforcement at AAC.

Table 1: Violations of Private Disciplinary Law and its Enforcement at AAC

No	Name	Official Position	Unit	GAR/Case	GAR/Case Detail	TMT	Additional Information
I	1. Mayor Cpn F. F. T, S.T.	Kabagbinkual & Kesbangan Sdirbinslambangja	AAC	Immoral conduct	- Delayed judicial decision at Court Martial II Jkt	23-11-2020	- Litigation
	2. Mayor Cpn F. F. T, S.T.	Kabagbinkual & Kesbangan Sdirbinslambangja	AAC	Domestic violence	- Delayed judicial process at appeal	01-12-2020	- Litigation
	3. Mayor Cpn F. F. T, S.T.	Kabagbinkual & Kesbangan Sdirbinslambangja	AAC	Defamation on social media	- Three-month imprisonment, five-month probation - <i>Tunda Dik</i> for 1 period and <i>tunda KP</i> for 3 periods since eligible	01-12-2020	- administrative sanction
	4. Lettu Cpn M. A. P.	Pama Puspenerbad	AAC	Fraud	- Process of Military Prosecutors Office II-08 Bandung	22-11-2021	- Litigation
	5. Lettu Cpn K. P.	Pama Puspenerbad	AAC	Desertion	- BHT 5-month imprisonment	31-10-2017	- delayed due to sickness
	6. Letda Cpn M. P. K.	Pama Puspenerbad	AAC	Road accident	- 2-month and 15-day imprisonment - <i>Tunda Dikcabpa</i> 1 period & <i>tunda KP</i> 3 periods since eligible	21-06-2018	- case closed
	7. Letda Cpn M. P. K.	Pama Puspenerbad	AAC	Desertion	- 11-month imprisonment	15-4-2021	- delayed administrative sanction
	8. Letda Cpn K. W.	Pama Puspenerbad	AAC	Immoral conduct	- Returning the case to Papera for settlement according to disciplinary law of privates	17-4-2021	- Anku Process
	9. Serda A. P. R.	Ba Puspenerbad	AAC	LGBT	- 5-month imprisonment and Dishonorable discharge	10-12-2020	- delayed definitive decision of the Chief of Staff of the Indonesian Army

II	PUSDIKPE NERBAD						
10.	Serka A. S.	Batitih Engine Depharsabang Pusdikpenerbad Puspenerbad	AAC (education center)	Desertion	- 5-month imprisonment - <i>Tunda Diktukpa</i> for 2 periods & <i>tunda KP</i> for 4 periods since eligible	06-09- 2020	- Admini strative sanction process
11.	Prada R. D. Y.	Taban Navrat Ton Demlat Kima	AAC (education center)	Desertion	- Denpom process IV/Dip	06-06- 2022	- Litigati on
III	LANUMAD A. YANI						
12.	Pratu M. A. R.	Ta Lanumad A. Yani Puspenerbad	Lanumad A. Yani	Immoral conduct	- Denpom process IV/Dip	2022	- Litigati on
IV	BENGPUS PENERBA D						
13.	Letkol Cpn Y. H.	Kabengjatlisira	Bengpus penerbad	Torture	- the imposition of disciplinary sanctions	12-04- 2019	- case closed
V	BALAKAD A PUSPENER BAD	NONE					
VI	LANUDAD GATOT SOEBROT O	NONE					
VII	SKADRON -11/SERBU						
14.	1. Peltu N. A. S.	Basiter Siintel Skadron-11/Serbu Puspenerbad	Skadron- 11/Serbu Puspenerbad	Accident causing death (road accident)	- <i>Tunda Diktukpa</i> for 2 periods	17-10- 2021	- Proses Sanktif
15.	2. Serma R. D. A. S. B.	Batihar Jatlisira Sihar Jatlisira Flitehar Dron- 11/Serbu	Skadron- 11/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	- Denpom process IV/Dip	18-05- 2022	- Proses Hukum
VII I	SKADRON -12/SERBU						
16.	Serda N. A. G.	Ba Skadron- 12/Serbu	Skadron- 12/Serbu Puspenerbad	Absence	- 4-month and 11-da imprisonment	23-7- 2021	- case closed
17.	Serda N. A. G.	Ba Skadron- 12/Serbu	Skadron- 12/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	-1-year and 6-month imprisonment preceded by dishonorable discharge	30-1- 2022	- case closed
18.	Serda Q. A.	Ba Skadron- 12/Serbu	Skadron- 12/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	Dishonorable discharge	5-6- 2020	- case closed
19.	Prada I K. D. P.	Ta Skadron- 12/Serbu	Skadron- 12/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	Dishonorable discharge	01-04- 2020	- cased closed
IX	SKADRON -13/SERBU						
20.	Prada W. S.	Tamudi Tonkes Dron-13/Serbu	Skadron- 13/Serbu Puspenerbad	Theft	- 7-month - Lapbangpri R/440/IX/2019	30-01- 2017	- Case closed

21.	Pratu R. S. E.	Taops Dron-13/Serbu	Skadron-13/Serbu Puspenerbad	Theft	tanggal 02 September 2019 - 8-month imprisonment - Lapbangpri R/437/IX/2019 dated on 02 September 2019	30-01-2017	- Case closed
22.	Pratu D. D. P. U.	Ta Provost Dron-13/Serbu	Skadron-13/Serbu Puspenerbad	Theft	- 7-month imprisonment - Lapbangpri R/438/IX/2019 dated on 02 September 2019	30-01-2017	- Case closed
23.	Prada B. A. Y.	Ta Kima Operator Dron-13/Serbu	Skadron-13/Serbu Puspenerbad	Theft	- 7-month imprisonment - Lapbangpri R/439/IX/2019 dated on 02 September 2019	30-01-2017	- Case closed
24.	Lettu Cpn N. T. I.	Pabang Siud I Flite C Heli Serbu Dron-13/Serbu	Skadron-13/Serbu Puspenerbad		- Pomdam process VI/MIW	01-08-2022	- Litigation
X SKADRON -21/SENA							
25.	Praka D. P.	Ta Skadron-21/Serbu	Skadron-21/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	Dishonorable discharge	04-01-2021	- litigation
26.	Pratu N. M.	Talisari Siud 1 Sabang Sena	Skadron-21/Sena Puspenerbad	Immoral conduct	- Court martial process II-07 Jakarta	17-06-2022	- Litigation
XI SKADRON -31/SERBU							
27.	Lettu Cpn M. A. P.	Pabang Siud II Flite A Heli Serbu	Skadron-31/Serbu Puspenerbad	Absence	- Closed	26-5-2020	- case closed
28.	Prada I G. S. S.	Ta Skadron-31/Serbu	Skadron-31/Serbu Puspenerbad	Desertion	- Dishonorable discharge	8-5-2020	- case closed

Sources: processed data

The above secondary data indicates that violations committed by the personnel of the Indonesian Armed Forces at AAC are across all levels ranging from enlisted personnel, non-commissioned officers, and commissioned officers with varied violations of military discipline and the severity of the violations. From 2017-2022, there had been 28 violations of military disciplinary law at AAC with the distribution of violations as shown in the following graph.

Graph 1: The number of violations on an annual basis

The total number of the personnel at AAC accounts for 372 members ranging from the lowest official rank, enlisted to the highest rank, consisting of 196 commissioned officers (lower-ranked officers, middle-ranked officers, flag officers), 92 non-commissioned officers, and 84 enlisted personnel. Of the total of 28 violations at AAC, the distribution of the violations committed by the personnel with varied official ranks ranging from enlisted personnel, non-commissioned officers, and commissioned officers (lower-ranked officers and middle-ranked officers) is presented in the following graph.

Graph 2: Distribution of violations according to official ranks

Compared to the number of personnel at every official rank with the number of violations within 6 years from 2017 to 2022, the highest percentage of the violations was found at enlisted rank, accounting for 84 members with 11 violations (13.09%), 92 non-commissioned officers with 7 violations (7.61%), while the lowest percentage of violations were found at the level of commissioned officers, accounting for 196 members with 10-time violations (5.10%).

The types of violations of military discipline and order commonly committed by the personnel at AAC vary but the desertion is dominant, accounting for 10 violations, followed by immoral conduct (4 violations), theft (4 violations), absence without any notification and road accident involving other persons as victims (2 violations),

and other categories (1) such as domestic violence, defamation, fraud, LGBT, torture, polygyny without consent of higher officials. The following graph provides the types of violations of military discipline and order at AAC from 2017 to 2022.

Graph 3: Number of Violators

Of the 28 violations of military discipline at IAFAAC from 2017 to 2022, almost half of the cases (13 cases or 46%) had been settled, while the rest were under litigation processes (9 cases or 32%), administrative sanctions (3 cases or 11%), and the rest was 1 case: *ankum* process, decision issuance process, and in-waiting for execution. The enforcement of military discipline for the personnel at AAC to help perform the tasks and functions in a general scope has been implemented according to the provisions of the legislation and the order applying to the domain of the Indonesian Armed Forces and specifically in the unit of AAC. This implementation can be measured through planning performed yearly along with a set of tasks and functions of the Central Implementing Body of AAC. Departing from this planning, each working unit of AAC executes the tasks and functions according to the domains and their authorities. The AAC embraces several working units within this scope: AAC headquarter, Army Aviation Education Center as an education unit stemming from Army Aviation Center right under Kodiklat TNI AD, Bengkel of Army Aviation Center, Procurement Agency at Army Aviation Center (Balakada Puspenerbad), Main Military Air Base Ahmad Yani Semarang, Military Air Base Gatot Subroto, headquarters detachment (Denma Puspenerbad), Squadron 11, Squadron 12, Squadron 13, Squadron 21, and Squadron 31.

The primary tasks and functions embedded in every unit are well implemented under the control of the Commander of AAC assisted by the Vice-Commander of AAC, the Inspector of AAC, and 2 (two) Directors of AAC. The measurement of performance can also be given by enforcing discipline to realize the enforcement of the law of military discipline and order within the domain of AAC.

What is interesting in this research is the high percentage of violations committed by the low-ranked personnel, where the violations committed by the enlisted personnel were as much as 13% of the total enlisted members of this rank. This significant percentage of violations can be triggered by several factors (Ramdani, n.d.): 1) Poor awareness of the law; in some cases of violations regarding discipline, insubordination, and other crimes committed by privates, it was found that most privates demonstrate a poor understanding of the law. They (privates) understand themselves as first-class citizens with superiority in law over civilians, undermining the rules of law represented by related institutions, police department, prosecutors, and courts. There is still a likelihood that privates only comply with their commander, and they even threaten police and other law enforcers in case of revealing the crimes they committed, 2) poor organizational culture may lead to practices harming discipline and professionalism, 3) social and cultural factors can affect the behavior of the members of the armed

forces, causing violations of discipline, 4) personal factors related to personal and emotional issues or personal problems can trigger the members of the armed forces to violate discipline, 5) poor motivation and psychological conditions can affect the behavior of the members of the armed forces causing disciplinary violations, 6) shortage of resources such as lack of supervision and control can lead further to disciplinary violations committed by the members of the armed forces, 7) inadequate, ineffective, and unjust sanctions will not deter military personnel from disciplinary violations, 8) leadership factor involves the absence of integrity and credibility, causing disciplinary violations in an organization, 9) family problem and economic burden may lead further to domestic violence or the condition where privates may be found to build other (illegal) careers outside the military scope such as those involved in gambling, serving as bodyguards, involved in a theft, robbery, and other criminal offenses due to unstable mentality of the privates.

Those are some of the myriad factors causing military disciplinary violations within the domain of armed forces, especially in the scope of AAC. Thus, some measures aiming to maintain and improve the discipline and professionalism of the personnel of the armed forces are required.

4. Measures to Improve the Discipline of Indonesian Armed Forces at AAC

Discipline is paramount for the success of the Indonesian Armed Forces. The law of military discipline helps form the structure ensuring that every member of the armed forces appropriately performs tasks and responsibilities. Furthermore, the enforcement of military discipline also ensures that the organization concerned can appropriately function and maintain security. Discipline can improve the professionalism of the members and guarantee that they behave accordingly and comply with professional standards. This is expected to bring positive impacts to help improve the trust of the members of the armed forces and to build a positive image and trust in an organization. In other words, the discipline in armed forces especially in the domain of AAC needs to be improved to guarantee that the organization can appropriately function and establish responsibilities and professionalism of the members and fulfill the tasks and obligations accordingly.

Several steps can be taken to help enforce military discipline within the scope of the Indonesian Armed Forces, especially at AAC: 1) strict law enforcement: the discipline among the personnel of the armed forces can be improved by strictly enforcing and imposing law on privates who commit violations. This approach will set an example implying that inappropriate conduct will lead to serious consequences and deterring effects, 2) consistent and sustainable training and education from the start can help build discipline and character of the privates. This can help ensure that privates understand the value and standards set for them, 3) administrative sanctions such as demotion, salary reduction, or transfer can be given to motivate privates to comply more with rules and standards and also help minimize violations, 4) the enforcement of rules and regulations must be consistently and justly applied to all privates since it will help ensure that equal standards apply to all and it is to imply that no discrimination is involved, 4) strong organizational culture should be based on disciplinary value and professionalism, which can help build the discipline among privates and to ensure that privates will adhere to their responsibilities and be dedicated to their tasks. Leaders can also provide incentives and rewards for privates who demonstrate a good disciplinary attitude and to set them as an example for others, 5) focus on career development will leave a chance for privates to adequately develop their career and education, and it is expected to motivate them to maintain the discipline and professionalism. A good career will help cut economic burdens as an issue causing disciplinary problems among privates. Career development of privates can take into account skill development, training in technology, management, and leadership, b) facilitating the participation of the personnel of the armed forces in internship programs and professional certifications to improve skills and open job opportunities after retirement, c) providing financial support and connectivity for those planning to set up a business after retirement, d) maintaining good relationships with companies and private institutions to help strengthen professional relationships and enhance job opportunities for the personnel of the armed forces after retirement, d) providing incentives for personnel involved in development projects aiming to enhance national economy, 6) openness and transparency in decision-making and actions must be implemented to ensure that privates are equally treated and feel recognized. This will also help build their career and grow solidarity among privates and serve as an essential factor in building discipline. The above measures are expected to create

harmonious, disciplinary, professional, and deterring conditions for the armed forces, especially in the scope of AAC.

5. Conclusion

Indonesian Armed Forces are a military organization strongly adhering to military discipline and ethics pursuant to *Sapta Marga* and the oath of enlistment. Thus, specific military traits deal with military disciplinary law serving as an instrument to ensure that the tasks and responsibilities of the armed forces, especially at AAC are performed professionally and accountably. Law Number 25 of 2014 concerning Military Disciplinary Law comprehensively governs the following matters: (1) the positions and the tasks of military disciplinary law in the Indonesian Armed Forces; (2) conduct that is subject to the imposition of disciplinary sanctions; (3) procedures and mechanisms of the enforcement of military disciplinary law; (4) elections and the tasks of disciplinary judges; and (5) protection for the personnel of Indonesian Armed Forces on whom disciplinary sanctions are imposed. Although legislation has set comprehensive regulations concerning the enforcement of military discipline, from 2017 to 2022 there had been at least 28 cases of disciplinary violations committed by privates within the domain of AAC. Some factors triggering violations involve poor awareness of the law, poor organizational culture, social and cultural factors, personal factors, motivation and psychological conditions, shortage of resources, adequate sanctions, leadership, family problems, and economic burdens. Thus, this research aims to formulate 7 strategies to improve the enforcement of disciplinary law among privates of the Indonesian Armed Forces at AAC; these strategies involve (1) strict law enforcement, (2) training and education, (3) administrative sanctions, (4) enforcement of rules and regulations, (5) strong organizational culture, (6) focus on career development, and (7) openness and transparency. Maximizing these strategies is expected to establish a harmonious environment for Indonesian Armed Forces, especially within the professional and disciplinary domain of AAC.

References

- Chandra, R. (2020). Penyelesaian Kasus Hukum di Lingkungan Pengadilan Militer dalam Perkara Tindak Pidana Penipuan yang Dilakukan oleh Anggota TNI [Settlement of Legal Cases in the Military Court in Fraud Cases Committed by Members of the Indonesian National Armed Forces]. *Pamulang Law Review*, 1(2), 75-86. <https://doi.org/10.32493/palrev.v1i2.5328>.
- House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia. (2009). Pidato Ketua DPR RI pada Penutupan Masa Persidangan III Tahun Sidang 2004-2005 [Speech by the Head of the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia at the Closing Session Period III for Year 2004-2005]. In *Himpunan Pidato, Sambutan dan Ceramah Pimpinan Dewan Perwakilan Rakyat Republik Indonesia Periode 2004-2009 [Collection of Speeches, Speeches and Lectures by the Leaders of the People's Representative Council of the Republic of Indonesia for the 2004-2009 Period]*. Sekretariat Jenderal DPR RI.
- Hadisancoko, R. E. (2019). Pembangunan Postur Pertahanan Militer yang Diarahkan pada Pembangunan Minimum Essential Force (MEF) TNI Menuju Terwujudnya Postur Ideal TNI [Development of a Military Defense Posture Directed at the Development of the TNI's Minimum Essential Force (MEF) Towards the Realization of the TNI's Ideal Posture]. *WIRA Media Informasi Kementerian Pertahanan, Biro Humas Setjen Kemhan*.
- Haryo Sulistiryanto. (2011). Pertanggungjawaban Pidana Anggota Militer TNI Yang Melakukan Tindak Pidana Desersi [Criminal Accountability of TNI Military Members Who Commit the Crime of Desertion]. *Perspektif: Kajian Masalah Hukum Dan Pembangunan*, 16(2), 82-94.
- Herawati, T., Nanda, H. S., Saputra, M. T., Yuliarty, R., & Widayanti, E. (2022). Implementasi Kebijakan Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 25 Tahun 2014 Tentang Hukum Disiplin Militer di Polisi Militer Daerah Militer II Sriwijaya [Policy Implementation of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2014 Concerning Military Discipline Law in the Military Police for Military Region II Sriwijaya]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Perbankan Syariah* 2(1), 155-170. <https://doi.org/10.36908/jimpa.v2i1.60>
- Pusat Pendidikan Markas Besar Tentara Nasional Indonesia. (2006, July 5). *Disiplin adalah Nafas Prajurit TNI { Discipline is the Breath of TNI Soldiers}*. <https://tni.mil.id/view-2945-disiplin-adalah-nafas-prajurit-tni.html>
- Pusat Penerangan Tentara Nasional Indonesia. (2014, Mei). *Pembinaan Hukum Sebagai Fungsi Komando Guna Mendukung Tugas Pokok TNI [Legal Guidance as a Command Function to Support the Main Duties of the TNI]*. <https://tni.mil.id/view-61921-pembinaan-hukum-sebagai-fungsi-komando-guna-mendukung-tugas-pokok-tni.html>

- Ramdani, R. D. N. (n.d.). *Menekan Pelanggaran Prajurit Melalui Kepemimpinan yang Efektif dan Penerapan Reward—Punishment [Suppressing Soldier Abuse Through Effective Leadership and Implementing Rewards—Punishment]*. Retrieved February 9, 2023, from <https://diskumal.tnial.mil.id/fileartikel/artikel-20180713-144205.pdf>.
- Saputra, R. Y. (2019). Penerapan Pasal 281 KUHP Tentang Tindak Pidana Asusila Yang Dilakukan oleh Militer (Studi Kasus Putusan Pengadilan Militer Nomor 127-K/PM.II09/AD/VIII/2017) [Implementation of Article 281 of the Criminal Code concerning Immoral Crimes Committed by the Military (Case Study of Military Court Decision Number 127-K/PM.II09/AD/VIII/2017)]. *Jurnal Hukum Adigama*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.24912/adigama.v2i1.5268>.
- Tambunan, A. (2005). *Hukum Militer Indonesia* (cet. pertama) [Indonesian Military Law (First Edition)]. Pusat Studi Hukum Militer Sekolah Tinggi Hukum Militer.
- Tentara Nasional Indonesia. (2023). *Sumpah Prajurit [Soldier's Oath]*. <https://tni.mil.id/pages-6-sumpah-prajurit.html>.
- Upe, T. (2011). *Optimalisasi Penyelenggaraan Bakti TNI dalam Rangka Pemberdayaan Wilayah Pertahanan Darat, Tentara Nasional Indonesia Angkatan Darat-Komando Daerah Militer VI/Mulawarman [Optimizing the Implementation of Indonesian National Armed Forces Service in the Context of Empowering Land Defense Areas, Indonesian National Armed Forces - Regional Military Command VI/Mulawarman]*. <https://tniad.mil.id/images/pdf/karmil-pama.pdf>
- Wulansari, E. M. (n.d.). *Hukum Disiplin Prajurit Tentara Nasional Indonesia (TNI) Paska Reformasi [Post-Reform Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) Disciplinary Law]*.
- Yogo, S. P. (2016). Spesialisasi dan Deferensiasi Peran TNI/ Polri dalam Strategi Pertahanan Keamanan Negara (Tanggapan terhadap RUU Kamnas) [Specialization and Differentiation of the Role of the Indonesian National Armed Forces / Indonesian National Police in the National Defense and Security Strategy (Response to the National Security Bill)]. *Jurnal Ilmu Kepolisian*, 806, 119-131.